

THE PROCESS OF ADAPTATION OF YOUNG PROFESSIONALS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Given the scientific nature of pedagogical technology, it can be explained as follows. Pedagogical technology is a new approach to the educational process, and pedagogy is an expression of social engineering consciousness. It is a social phenomenon associated with the pedagogical process of creating an optimal lesson plan based on the technical possibilities and human technical thinking. This means that the role of pedagogical technologies in the teaching of social sciences and humanities is great. Without them, the goal cannot be achieved.*

Keywords— elementary school, distance learning, manual, computer, goal, time, teacher, gadgets, preschool education.

1. INTRODUCTION

The term technology is derived from production, in which thousands of technological processes are designed. They are the key to achieving the desired results. When these technologies are used, even if the region and their executors change, they will still produce the desired product. Pedagogical technology will be developed to achieve this in the educational process.

In pedagogical technology, along with a special method, the method of development, research is also used. The formation of independent free citizens requires the training of specialists with a certain level of knowledge necessary for the national economy, as well as entrepreneurs who seek and solve various problems. In the upbringing of such people, the product of teaching typical actions and research methods that learn to find a way out of non-standard situations are compatible. Pedagogical technology makes good use of the range of methods we need: The main difference between the traditional methods and techniques of pedagogical technology is that it is derived from the theory of complexes, which is subject to all the laws of this theory.

2. MAIN PART

Today, the teaching of children in preschool institutions, i.e. on other special issues, is becoming a topical issue on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, i.e. modern interactive methods. One of the main issues is the use of teaching skills in the process of teaching letters, effective organization of the teaching process, adaptation to educational standards, raising to world standards, perfect formation of knowledge and skills of teaching foreign languages to students. is one of the important factors in the lime process. Modern technologies for interactive language teaching are being developed and used effectively in the classroom. The main difference between modern interactive methods and traditional methods is that students are free in the process of learning foreign languages, think independently, have the opportunity

to express their opinions, engage in discussions, communicate freely with the teacher.

In the process of teaching science on the basis of modern interactive methods, the following is done:

- Students plan and actively participate in the lessons; students practice independently and strengthen their knowledge according to the established curriculum.
- Students engage in a discussion on the topic during the lesson and all actively participate in it;
- Students participate as partners in the selection and implementation of teaching methods, express their views;
- Students are provided with the opportunity to describe and explain their knowledge, that is, to share it with others;

Of course, all of the above can help students achieve a step-by-step process of learning languages through interactive methods.

The following technologies of interactive methods are widely used in foreign language learning today:

1. Interactive game mode.
2. Methods of active participation of students in pairs and in groups.
3. The method of mental observation.
4. Type of frontal training.
5. Aquarium method.
6. Brownian motion method.
7. Incomplete speech method.
8. How to take your place.
9. Discussion and other similar methods.

The interactive method of teaching is based on the above-mentioned modern technologies, as a result of which the student's knowledge and skills of independent thinking and speaking are perfectly formed. Their freedom is created during

the lesson, which means that students set their own goals and objectives, discuss, debate, and finally draw conclusions on the topic being studied.

In general, students play a leading role in the interactive method of teaching, which is determined by their excellent command of a foreign language, the ability to express themselves independently, that is, the ability to speak fluently.

In the early twentieth century, the American philosopher, psychologist and educator John Dewey argued that the student should be active, not the teacher, in the classroom. He argued that dry memorization of knowledge in a book does not lead to anything, but rather cools students from reading and corrupts their thinking.

Group activities can be organized in the following ways:

1. Each group performs the tasks given by the teacher according to the general scheme, and at the end of the lesson the relations of the groups are summarized on the project items.

2. The groups perform the tasks given by the teacher on separate points of the general scheme.

Learning activities are organized according to the following scheme, which is reflected directly on the board or worksheet:

I Know-I want to Know-I know. The method is based on three steps:

1. The level of students' understanding of the topic to be studied is determined.

2. Students' needs to enrich their existing knowledge on the topic are explored.

3. Students will be introduced to the topic in detail.

The full details of the steps taken are as follows.

- Students are assigned to groups;
- The level of students' understanding of a new topic is studied;
- The concepts mentioned by students are written in one point of the project;
- The needs of students to enrich their existing knowledge on a new topic are studied;
- The concepts described as needs of students are written in two points of the project;
- The teacher informs students with general information on a new topic;
- new concepts learned by students are identified;
- the described new concepts are written in the third point of the project;
- At the end of the training a single project will be created.

3. CONCLUSION

The use of modern technologies in language teaching is very important, and it requires a great deal of skill, more work on himself, sufficient knowledge, skills and competencies.

It is known that the teaching profession, unlike other professions, involves a multifaceted responsibility, firstly, it is the formation of personality, that is, a deep knowledge of the human psyche, and secondly, all the means, methods and methods of education and to organize the educational process effectively, that is, to achieve the effectiveness of teaching, and thirdly, to form its own qualities in the process of development of society and nature. The teacher must shape the personality of the younger generation in accordance with the requirements of society. If every educator organizes the educational process correctly, the level of mastery of the student will be higher.

4. REFERENCES

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